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The Implementation of Role Play in Teaching Future Tense

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Abstract: Future tense is one of important part of daily communication, students need to know the future tense well otherwise they get misunderstanding of speakers' purpose. Some students get confused and have difficulties in defining part of a sentence. So, it is important for them to know the tense well. Moreover, the purpose of this study was to know about the improvement of student's future tense understanding after they were taught by using role play. This research used a quantitative approach and it was conducted to 15 students in class 2019 semester 1. The data of the research collected using a paper based test of future tense. The result showed that there was significant improvement in students' future tense understanding after they got role play. It could be proven from the improvement of students' average score from the pretest and post-test, which was 59 to 82,6, hypothesis test showed that t-table is 2,145 and the t-value is 14,992. In conclusion, role play technique can improve students' future tense understanding

Keywords: *Role play, future tense*

INTRODUCTION

Future Tense is a type of tenses which can inform about a plan which hasn't been done yet. Some students don't care about this type of grammar because they think that it is not really important. On the contrary, future tense is one of the tenses which is very important in our daily activity. We can simply tell our plan by telling them in the future

tense, we don't need to explain more because they know that it hasn't happened yet. So, the awareness of future tense is very important. Most students get bored studying grammar because they have to remember the rule while they are communicating. Some of them are eager to check it in other sources, but some of them give up and don't want to study grammar. Some teachers thought that when we study a language we only need to try or practice that language, but on the other hand, grammar is very important in studying English to distinguish the meaning and when the event happens. As Debata (2013) said that most persons who communicate with a chosen language will be aware of the grammar.

Students should use grammar when they have a communication with others. Michaelis (2008) mentioned that speakers will use present tense to inform about their present activities and use future tense to tell something that happened in the future. It is why the future tense is very important to understand when the event happens. We have to recognize the grammar to help us understand the context and the sentences. It is also stated in Dibdyaningsih (2018) that grammar is important in achieving several types of tests and it is important to divine time or event. So, grammar, especially future tense, is an important lesson in learning a new language. Moreover, Wright, Betteridge and Buckby (2005) stated that language learning is very hard and efforts are required over a long period of time. To avoid this, lectures should teach using new strategies.

Based on the explanation, we conclude that tense is one of good tools for students to understand the new language. It also refers to the fact that when students cannot understand the tense, they will meet difficulties in understanding sentences. Sometimes, students know the word in meaning but they cannot understand the context because it has different meanings when it applies different tense.

In addition, role play is an activity which makes language learning fun and triggers students to be active in the class. Learners of new language have to deal with future tense rules during their acquisition. In order to learn and practice future tense rules, students should participate in role play activities in their classroom. The activities also include future tense practice which especially focus on helping students develop and apply future tense in different contexts by making the class enjoyable.

Therefore, it is necessary to explore whether students learn future tense rules effectively through *role play* and how they learn it. Normally students memorize the rules of future tense in a list, and when they fail with this way, they will say that it is caused by their weak analysis. Research and publications have shown that this is not a very effective way to study. Wright, Betteridge and Buckby (2005) stated that language learning needed efforts and required over a long period of time. Special attention is given to the problems related to teaching and learning grammar.

Moreover, Sadat (2017) said that lecture should blend teaching future tense with communicative language teaching in order to achieve the future tense understanding. How lectures apply to any technique to teach future tense will influence a student's future tense understanding. It is because when they aren't interested in the teaching process, they will ignore the lecture and do anything else, it will make them unable to understand what the lecture has explained. So, lecture should develop a creative and interactive media in teaching grammar.

Studying grammar can be used in many different techniques. One of the learning techniques that is used in STKIP Al Hikmah Surabaya is 'role play' that seems to have many benefits for those who are studying grammar. Thus, this study was conducted to identify how 'role play' may facilitate the teaching process and help students to study grammar. And it has tried to find out whether 'role play' can improve students' future tense understanding. So, from the explanation above, this study was focused on the improvement of students' future tense understanding after they were taught by using role play. The problem of this study is to find out whether there is any significant improvement of students' future tense understanding after they were taught using role play.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study was quantitative research which used one group pretest and posttest design. The population of this study was the 2019 class of the first semester students in STKIP Al Hikmah Surabaya. This class consists of 15 students. In determining that sample, the researcher used Random Sampling Technique. In this study, the researcher

used the paper based test by filling missing words in a sentence as the instrument. The researcher started the research by conducting the pre-test. The researcher administered pre-test before treatment. It was aimed at knowing the students' future tense understanding before being given the treatment using role play technique. In administering the pre-test, the researcher chose the topic. Then, the students have to sit in pairs to have role play then finally fulfilling the blank space of sentences given with the appropriate words in future tense. Pre-test was similar to the posttest. The researcher saved the result of the test.

After the pre-test, the students were taught using role play technique. There were three treatments. In the treatment, the researcher used role play in teaching future tense in the class. First, the researcher started the meeting by brainstorming the students' then they were divided into pairs. The researcher gave them role play paper for each pair, the paper consists of a short story in the future tense without any detailed dialogue and the pair have to pretend as the characters in that story. The researcher makes sure that every pair has a different topic for each meeting. After the students get the story they will create and practice the detail dialog about the story in future tense form. After all pairs presented their dialogue, the researcher evaluated and gave them corrections related to it. Then, the researcher gave them some examples of doing role play. The treatments were implemented in three meetings with the same procedures.

Then, the researcher administered the post-test after the treatment. It was for knowing the difference of students' future tense understanding after they have taught by using role play in grammar class. Post-test was similar to pre-test. In administering post-test, the researcher chose one topic for the students. Then, the students had a discussion in peer. They had to complete missing words in future sentences.

Then, in order to see whether there was an improvement of students' future tense understanding, the researcher examined the students' scores using the key answer list. The raw scores were tabulated and calculated using repeated measures T-test of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) for Windows version 16 to test whether there is an improvement or not.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

This study was conducted in 5 meetings: first, the researcher administered a pretest. In the second, third, and fourth meeting, the researcher conducted the treatment by using role play. In the fifth meeting, the researcher administered post-test to find out the students' improvement in understanding future tense after they were taught by using role play.

The researcher analyzes the scores of the pre-test and the post-test in the experimental class. The researcher was conducted on March 8th- April 7th, 2020. At the first meeting, the researcher conducted a pretest to find out the students' future tense understanding before the treatments. The researcher administered the pre-test for 50 minutes. The material of the test was a short story. The researcher used fill in the blank test in the pretest. The researcher scored the pre-test.

Table 4.1 Students' Score in Future Tense Test

Number of students	Pre-Test Score	Post-Test Score	Increasing score
1	55	75	20
2	45	70	25
3	65	85	20
4	35	75	40
5	40	65	25
6	75	95	20
7	65	90	25
8	55	75	20
9	80	100	20
10	55	85	30
11	60	80	20
12	70	90	20
13	65	95	30
14	60	85	25
15	60	75	15

From the statistical calculation formula by using SPSS 16, it was found that there was an increase between the average score of the pre-test and post-test. The average score in the pre-test was 59, meanwhile the score in the posttest was 82,6. It was also found that t-value was 8.621, in which the data based on t-table was at least 2.145. Thus, t-value was higher than t-table ($8.621 > 2.145$) and the two tails showed that $p < 0.05$ ($p = .000$). Therefore, it could be stated that between pre-test and post-test score there is an increase in students' future tense understanding.

Based on the result of the research, it can be seen that the students got a higher score in the post-test. Shortly, there was an improvement of students' future tense understanding after being taught using role play. However, from the data above, we can know that the hypothesis proposed by the researcher was accepted. The hypothesis proposed by the researcher is, there is improvement in students' future tense understanding after being taught using role play as teaching technique was accepted. Finally, the researcher can conclude that role play technique can be a good technique of teaching future tense. After implementing this technique, students got improvement from the first until the last treatment.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the data analysis and discussion, the researcher concludes that there was a significant improvement of the students' future tense understanding from the pretest and posttest after they were being taught by using role play technique. Role play technique is applicable to encourage the students to improve their grammar understanding. It could be proven from the improvement of the students' mean scores in the pretest and the posttest. The result of the posttest was higher than the result of the pretest. The mean score of the pretest was 59, and then, it increased in the post-test up to 82,6. Learning process using Role play makes the students can build self-confidence and solve their problem by themselves. By practicing a lot, there will be an improvement of students' future tense understanding.

Based on the conclusion the researcher suggests the English teacher be able to make some variation of topics in teaching future tense so that the students will be interested in learning English. In implementing this technique, the teacher should give more attention to the students' awareness of future tense sentences.

REFERENCES

- Debata, Pradeep. (2013). The Importance of Grammar in English Language Teaching: A Reassessment. Language in India.
- Michaelis, Laura. (2008). Tense in English. 10.1002/9780470753002.ch10.
- Abdul Majeed, Mohamed. (2018). Teaching Grammar in the English Language Classroom: Perceptions and Practices of Students and Teachers in the Ampara District
- Coe, Norman. (2012). Oxford Living Grammar: Intermediate. Retrieved from <https://elt.oup.com/student/livinggrammar/int/?cc=id&selLanguage=id>
- Dibdyaningsih, Haris. (2018). The Role of "Magic Box" in Innovating Media in Teaching Grammar. 10.31227/osf.io/y35kc.
- Harrison, Mark. (2009). Oxford Living Grammar: Pre – Intermediate. Retrieved from <https://elt.oup.com/student/livinggrammar/pre/?cc=id&selLanguage=id>
- Paterson, Ken. (2012). Oxford Living Grammar: Upper – Intermediate. Retrieved from <https://elt.oup.com/student/livinggrammar/upper/?cc=id&selLanguage=id>
- Paterson, Ken. (2009). Oxford Living Grammar: Elementary. Retrieved from <https://elt.oup.com/student/livinggrammar/ele/?cc=id&selLanguage=id>
- Sadat, M. (2017). Revisiting the Debate of Grammar Teaching: A Young Scholar's Perspective. Sino-US English Teaching, 14(1), 1-7.
- Wright, A., Betteridge, D., & Buckby, M. (2005). Games for language learning (3rd ed.). New York: Cambridge University.